

Material Design for Reduction of Blisters in SMC

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ABSTRACT

Blisters on SMC parts have caused problems for compression moulders for many years and experimental studies have led to reasonably effective preventive actions. The effect on material peak temperature and curing time for a change of polyester/LS additive ratio, added α -methyl styrene and alumina trihydrate (ATH) for 10 SMC formulations are discussed in this work. Temperature and pressure sensors were installed at different locations in the mould to examine changes in temperature and internal mould pressure during moulding at various process conditions. A reduction of the maximum temperature at the centreline of the material could be observed for the three investigated components. Furthermore, it is shown that a linear correlation between maximum temperature and curing time exist. A reduction in material peak temperature lead to an increased curing time.

Keywords: SMC, compression moulding, blister, material design, α -methyl styrene.

1. INTRODUCTION

The usage of Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC) details are several and one important market segment can be found in the electrical field. Some typical products can be represented by electrical switchers, lamp housings and bus supports etc. Due to mass production and cost reductions, current attentions is mainly focused on activities concerning low-cost material, improvement of quality and development of the production method.

A common way to reduce the cost level for SMC moulded parts is to lower or to eliminate the number of rejected parts. One of the quality problem occurring is blistering on moulded parts. Depending on part design, moulding equipment, SMC-formulations and current process conditions different types of defects appear. From time to time blisters can reach level as high as 5% - 10% of the produced quantity. Previous work at SICOMP [1] concerning the effect of critical moulding conditions for blistering of LS-SMC, indicates that a high centreline temperature in the SMC-material resulted in blistering for moulded parts, see Figure 1. Temperatures up to 230 °C was observed and this only for moulded parts with 4.8 mm in thickness. A simple preventive action as increased mould pressure or increased pressing speed resulted in a reduction of blisters on moulded parts.

Since SMC is a poor conductor of heat it will take a certain time for heating. A high temperature will be observed in the SMC-material due to the simple fact that heat cannot quickly escape during

moulding and a build up of heat will occur when the curing reaction starts [2]. A change of thermal properties for SMC-materials by adding ingredients with lower thermal conductivity [3] or retarding the curing reaction [4] will consequently damp out the exothermic temperature peak and lower the maximum temperature.

A possible way to decrease the number of moulded parts with blisters is to reduce the maximum temperature at the centreline. From time being, the general approaches to control the curing process is to use different types of inhibitors and initiators [5, 6]. In this paper the main efforts are directed to investigate the effects of three material components on the maximum temperatures observed inside the SMC-material during moulding. This can be attainable by retarding the free radical copolymerisation reaction of styrene and unsaturated polyester, or by changing the thermal properties by adding ATH or changing the ratio of polyester resin and thermoplastic additive (LS-additive).

Ten different SMC-materials were manufactured on a SMC machine and after maturing the SMC process was followed by compression moulding in a instrumented mould for measurements of internal pressure and temperature. The purpose is to reduce the exothermic temperature peak and to achieve a low temperature profile in the SMC during moulding and in this way reduce the number of rejected parts due to blistering.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The Low Shrink (LS) SMC-materials used in these experiments were kindly manufactured at Jotun Polymer A.S., Sandefjord (Norway). Ten different SMC-material were produced on a rebuild Finn & Fram SMC-machine. The detailed recipes are listed in Table 1. All ingredients are commercially available and all formulations contain 20% chopped glass fibres by weight and 25.4 mm in length.

2.2 Compression moulding equipment

A 3100 kN Fjellman press was used for compression moulding. The Fjellman press is equipped with a multiprocessor control system which enables an active control of table parallelism, pressing force, temperature and closing speed during the last 30 mm closing and during curing. Each table is electrically heated in six zones. Positions from each corner of the upper table (corner separation), closing speed, temperature and pressing force are continuously measured and data are transformed to ASCII files via a high-speed data acquisition system.

2.3 Instrumentation of the mould

A flat circular mould, with a cavity of 300 mm in diameter was instrumented. One advantage of this geometry is that the flow pattern is rather simple if a circular charge is employed. For measurements of pressure two Kistler quartz sensors (Type 6151 C) were flush mounted in the upper mould, one placed in the centre, another placed 5 mm from the shear edge. The output signal from the pressure sensors were connected to the Fjellman press data processing system. Thermocouples were lead inside the mould through the side wall of the lower mould half. A detachable block with machined slots for the thermocouples made it possible for measurements of temperature inside the charge at the centreline.

2.4 Experimental procedure

All moulding was performed on the Fjellman 310 ton hydraulic press with accompanying data acquisition and control system. The press variables pressing force, mould temperature and closing speed could be pre-set by the operator to give the moulding conditions. Details of the press variables for two different process conditions are listed in Table 2.

A 3-factor experimental design were carried out to evaluate the contributions for three components (factors) in the SMC formulation. The independent variables (factors) of interest were:

Component	Function	Level (-)	Level (+)
Alumina trihydrate (ATH)	Lowering the thermal conductivity	0	50 parts
α -methyl styrene	Retarding of the curing reaction	0	4 parts
Polyester/LS-additive ratio	Decrease of the polyester resin level	70/30	60/40

The first component ATH was added to the formulation and in the same time replacing one third of CaCO_3 . The second component α -methyl styrene was replacing the otherwise added styrene monomer. Finally, the composition of (Polyester/LS-additive) was change from 70/30 ratio to 60/40, based on 100 parts by weight of resin [phr]. The 3-factor experimental design is depicted in Table 3. Included is also two extra SMC formulations as references.

Before moulding operations the manufactured SMC material were taken from ≈ 30 kg SMC-rolls, first cut into easy handling pieces and then cut into square parts 176 mm in length. The single parts or the SMC layers were stacked into a pile and each layer was turned 30° so a circular shaped charge were formed. Each layer had roughly a weight of 100 g. The number of SMC layers was set to 4 or 6 and the weight for the charge was constant and 450 g respectively 600 g. Adjustment of weight consisted of smaller pieces and they were placed below the top layer. The stacked pile charge was then placed in the centre of the mould and the press was activated. The total cycle time depended on dwelling time, closing speed and curing time and ranged from 185 seconds up to 190 seconds. The curing time was set to 180 seconds. After moulding the finished parts were visually examined for blisters and other surface defects.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Measurements of internal mould pressure at the centre of the mould and temperature inside the charge have been the tool for analysing the influence of the different SMC formulations. Figure 2 shows measured centreline temperature and the centre pressure variations for a moulding cycle. The complex pressure variations during moulding can be explained by the curing behaviour of the SMC. Cure does not occur simultaneously over the whole part, but starts at the edge of the part and propagates towards it centre. The first part of the pressure curve represents the flow of the SMC during closing followed by an immediate increase in pressure when the mould is closed. The pressure curves shows a distinct pressure peak if the cross linking reaction propagates from the edge into the centre without any disturbance. A time period of interest is the curing time period Δt which is defined as the difference between the ending of the pressure peak t_2 and the time to initiation t_1 ($\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$). This time difference Δt represents the overall curing time period from the edge into the centre.

The temperature variations at the centreline of the SMC during moulding can easily be recognised and the heating to mould temperature are followed by the exothermic temperature peak and the maximum temperature can be observed. The time period from closed mould to the maximum temperature t_3 is also of interest and coincide with the t_2 time period defined in the pressure curves.

3.1 Maximum Temperature

The maximum temperature (T_{\max}) measured at the centreline of the SMC-material was observed for ten different SMC formulation. Figure 3 shows the T_{\max} as a function of the different SMC-materials. Materials (1 - 8) are related to the designed experiment and materials 9 and 10 are included as reference and contain 100 parts of polyester resins for material number 9 and 150 parts ATH for material number 10. Mouldings were performed at two different process conditions, see Table 2. In Figure 3 descending values of the T_{\max} for both process conditions can be observed as

a function of the SMC formulations. The purposed effect of reducing maximum temperature was accomplished and the maximum temperatures drop almost 20 °C for mouldings at both types of process conditions. The reference mouldings shows almost the same broad range of T_{\max} as the designed experiment. This is obvious because SMC-material 9 is highly reactive and generates a high maximum temperature. The increased thermal conductivity for SMC-material 10 results in a reduction of the maximum temperature T_{\max} .

According to Yates's algorithm [7] the effect of each component can be calculated. A change of the variable of interest (factor) from the average levels for all factors to the high level will be evaluated. A suitable variable to analyse in this respect is the difference between T_{\max} and the measured mould temperature, T_{mould} , which will represent the increase of temperature due to the curing reaction ($\Delta T = T_{\max} - T_{\text{mould}}$). The effects of the different factors are presented in Table 4. A change of 4 parts of styrene monomer to 4 parts of α -methyl styrene monomer will result in a reduction of the ΔT by 12 % (-3.8 °C) for mouldings at process conditions 1 and reduces ΔT by 16 % (-7.5°C) for process conditions 2.

The most important conclusions in this analysis is that the added ingredients have a pronounced influence on reducing the maximum temperature. The effects of the ratio of polyester/LS-additive and α -methyl styrene are obvious during mouldings for both process conditions and the effect of ATH is only notable for the ΔT during process conditions 1. The second observation is that no interaction between the three ingredients were observed. Table 4 also shows the effect of the time to T_{\max} , t_3 for the three investigated factors. In this cases the time to maximum temperature will increase and the effect for α -methyl styrene can be observed for both process conditions.

3.2 The effect of added components on the curing time period

Figure 4 shows the effect on curing time period (Δt) for the different SMC formulations during mouldings at the two process conditions. The Δt 's are defined from the pressure curves and increases depending on the added components. This will result in a retarding of the curing reaction and a change the thermal properties for the SMC-materials. The reference materials will also in this case have the same range of Δt as the designed materials. The added α -methyl styrene and polyester/LS-additive ratio have the most pronounced effects, see Table 4. The effect on observed parameters Δt are also calculated for the different factors according to Yates's algorithm.

3.3 The effect of curing rate on the temperature profile

The maximum temperature T_{\max} was plotted as a function of the curing time period Δt for the different materials and at the two process conditions, see Figure 5. A general trend can be observed and a decrease of the maximum temperature T_{\max} results in a longer or extended curing time period Δt . Even if a rather large scatter of experimental results exist a calculation of the linear correlation between T_{\max} and Δt was performed. In this special case the slope at the two process conditions has almost the same value and is calculated to -2.78 respectively -2.72 [°C/s]. The conclusion from the study is that a decrease of maximum temperature T_{\max} can be observed for an increased curing time period Δt independent on the moulding conditions and material formulations. Of course, initiator, inhibitor system and polyester resin types and fibre reinforcements have also an important roll for the control of the curing reaction. Nevertheless, this is one way to decrease extreme temperature peaks and to reduce the blister formation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Change levels of polyester resin/LS-additive ratio, α -methyl styrene and added ATH in the SMC formulations resulted in a reduction of the maximum temperature at the centreline in the SMC charge during moulding (20 °C). In the same time an extended curing time period was observed and the exothermic temperature peak will be damped by using the above mentioned components. The 3-factor experimental design shows that the change level of polyester/LS additive has the most pronounced effect on reducing the T_{\max} or ΔT followed by the added α -methyl styrene component. The recommendations for an optimal design of a SMC-material are to decrease the level of polyester

resin and to add a minor amount of α -methyl styrene. This will reduce T_{max} and only increase the total curing time (t_3) by a few seconds. Furthermore, no interactions between the three investigated components were found. All the results shows that a decrease of the maximum temperature T_{max} will occur for an increased curing time period Δt independent on the moulding conditions and material formulations.

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TABLE 1
Formulations for 10 different SMC material, based on 100 parts resin [phr].

SMC-formulation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ingredient										
Polyester resin	70	70	70	70	60	60	60	60	100	65
LS-additive	30	30	30	30	40	40	40	40	—	35
Styrene	4	4	—	—	4	4	—	—	4	4
α -methyl styrene	—	—	4	4	—	—	4	4	—	—
Initiator, Trigonox C	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
Inhibitor, Hydroquinone	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Thickener, MgO Paste	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Filler 1, CaCO ₃	150	100	150	100	150	100	150	100	150	—
Filler 2, ATH	—	50	—	50	—	50	—	50	—	150

TABLE 2
Moulding conditions for the Fjellman 3100 kN Hydraulic press.

Variables	Unit	Process Conditions 1	Process Conditions 2
Mould Temperature	[°C]	160	160
Mould Pressure	[MPa]	10	10
Pressing speed	[mm/s]	5	30
Charge weight	[kg]	4.50	6.00

TABLE 3
3-Factor Experimental Design, trials and ingredients [phr] in the formulation

Factor	(-)	(+)	Trial (Formulation)	A	B	C
A. ATH	0	50	1	-	-	-
B. α -methyl styrene	0	4	2	+	-	-
C. Polyester resin/ LS-additive ratio.	70/30	60/40	3	-	+	-
			4	+	+	-
			5	-	-	+
			6	+	-	+
			7	-	+	+
			8	+	+	+
			9	0	0	100
			10	150	0	65/35

TABLE 4
Effect of the 3-Factor Experimental Design on observed Temperature and Time parameters, [%] changes based on average for 8 trials.

Factor	ΔT		t_3		Δt	
	*(PC-1)	(PC-2)	(PC-1)	(PC-2)	(PC-1)	(PC-2)
A. ATH	-13	-2	2	3	3	14
B. α -methyl styrene	-12	-16	6	8	13	15
C. Polyester resin/ LS-additive ratio.	-24	-13	1	2	17	13
Average	32.4	48 [°C]	50.8	67.7 [s]	14.5	13.3 [s]

*PC short for Process Conditions.

Figure 1. Mould pressure vs. maximum temperature in the centreline. Symbols represents moulded parts at various process conditions. The line separates accepted parts from moulded parts with blisters.

Figure 2. Mould pressure at the centre of the mould and centreline Temperature vs. time during moulding. Parameter t_1 represents the time to initiation of the curing reaction, t_3 (t_2) gives the time to maximum temperature respectively ending of the pressure peak. Finally Δt represents the curing time period.

Figure 3. Maximum Temperature vs. SMC-material formulations. The temperature is measured at the centreline of the SMC charge during moulding for 10 different material formulations and during two process conditions (PC)

Figure 4. Curing time period vs. SMC formulations and during moulding at two different process conditions (PC). The parameter Δt is defined from measurements of the internal mould pressure at the centre of the mould.

Figure 5. The maximum temperature vs. curing time period during mouldings at two process conditions (PC). Lines show the linear correlations.